

**HISTORY OF THE SCIENCE OF CONFLICTOLOGY
AND ITS ROOTS**

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Annotation :To understand the science of conflictology, it is necessary to turn to ancient philosophy, within the framework of which an attempt was made to understand the world rationally for the first time. Ancient views on conflict were built on the basis of the philosophical doctrine of contradictions. This article talks about the history of conflictology and its development.

Key words: sociology, society, conflictology, psychology, antic, method.

INTRODUCTION

The term conflictology is one of the youngest branches of scientific knowledge, developed at the intersection of many disciplines, primarily sociology and psychology. Conflictology appeared as a relatively independent direction in sociology at the end of the 50s of the 20th century and was initially called "conflict sociology". Studies in conflict sociology and especially conflict psychology contributed to the development of conflictological practice. The formation of the practice of conflict management took place in the 70s of the 20th century. During this period, Horowitz and Boardman created a psychological training program aimed at teaching constructive behavior in conflictual relationships. Charles Oswood developed the GRID (Gradual and Reciprocal Initiatives to Reduce Tensions) methodology for international conflict resolution. In the development of the practice of conflict management, negotiation methods of conflict resolution took a special place (D. Scott; S. and G. Bower; G. Kelman, etc.). The development of negotiation technologies with the participation of a mediator (V.Lincoln, L.Thompson, R.Rubin, etc.) led to the creation of educational

institutions for training specialist mediators in the USA in the 70s and 80s. During this period, R. Fisher and V. Urey's method of "principled negotiations" at Harvard gained worldwide fame. In the 80s, conflict management centers appeared in the United States and other countries of the world. In 1986, on the initiative of the United Nations, the International Center for Conflict Resolution was established in Australia. The first conflict resolution center in Russia was established in St. Petersburg in the early 1990s. Before the emergence of conflictology as a relatively independent theory and practice in the late 50s, there was a long period of formation, accumulation and development of conflictological ideas and views within the framework of philosophy, and later within the framework of sociology, psychology and other sciences. In this regard, it is important to analyze the evolution of scientific views on the conflict, to distinguish the following periods.

Ancient times In this period, the views of ancient Chinese thinkers deserve attention. Confucius (551-479 BC), one of the first Chinese philosophers, has a special place among them. His philosophical ideas, including conflictology, were developed by other Chinese thinkers over many centuries. Analyzing ancient views on the problem of conflict, we should pay attention to the fact that many thinkers of that time connected them with the context of social events not only by determining the causes of various conflicts (conflicts), but also by evaluating them.

But war came to the attention of ancient thinkers not only as a social conflict. Interesting conflictological ideas related to the structure of the state can be found, for example, in Aristotle (384-322 BC), who argued that the state is an instrument that reconciles people. A person outside the state, in his opinion, is aggressive and dangerous. The socio-ethical and legal ideas of Democritus are also of interest, he said that "laws do not forbid everyone to live according to their own taste, if everyone does not do evil to each other, envy helps to start enmity". The most important feature of the conflictual ideas developed in the views of medieval thinkers is that they are mainly of a religious nature.

It is important to understand the socio-cultural conditions and social structure

of that period when analyzing the conflictological views of the thinkers of the New Age and the Age of Enlightenment. First of all, it was a period of not only strong economic, but also incomparable cultural growth of European countries. All this created the necessary conditions for a systematic approach to the study of the phenomena of the surrounding world, including conflicts. The most characteristic views on the conflict for the considered period were in the works of Francis Bacon (1561 - 1626), Thomas Hobbes (1588-1679), Jean-Jacques Rousseau (1712-1778), Adam Smith (1723-1790).), and so on. In particular, F. Bacon was one of the first to use a systematic approach to the analysis of the causes of social conflicts within the country. In this sense, T. Hobbs's concept of "war of all against all" about the natural state of society is interesting.

The relationship of conflictology with other disciplines is revealed in the following two aspects. The first aspect is that conflictology is based on the principles of knowledge developed within other disciplines and allows a deeper understanding of the subject of conflictology research. These principles are: principles of universal communication; determinism; development; systematic approach; social and activity context; personal approach; addition etc. The second aspect of the problem is the creative use of research methods of other disciplines by conflictology. When talking about the relationship of conflictology with other disciplines, one cannot fail to note its negative impact on these disciplines. For example, conflictological problems in the field of interpersonal relations stimulate the solution of many psychological, sociological, legal and ethical problems, in particular, communication, relationships, socio-psychological climate and many other problems. Conflictology is an interdisciplinary science that uses the achievements of other disciplines and provides them with its research results. However, the relationship between conflict studies and these disciplines is different. With which of them does conflictology have the closest and strongest connection? Conflictology closely cooperates with the following disciplines:

philosophy (in particular, social philosophy and dialectics), because the

dialectical principle of the philosophy of the unity and struggle of opposites, which explains the mechanism of the development of everything, is also based on the explanation of the essence of conflict, which is the result of conflict. Conflict of opposites, therefore, conflictology is based on the theory of conflict developed in dialectical-materialistic philosophy. The use of concepts of unity and struggle of contradictions, resolution of contradictions, typology of contradictions makes it possible to consider conflictology as a form of concretization of dialectics in philosophical, anthropological and socio-cultural problems. Interpersonal and interpersonal conflicts), psychology that studies psychological approaches to their understanding, analysis of human interaction in conflict situations (including conflict psychology). A person's experience of conflicts, features of providing psychological support to people in the event of conflicts, etc. Conflict psychology requires a good knowledge of many psychological problems of personality theory, its structure, motivational component, mental processes, personality typology, volitional, emotional, unconscious processes. Sociology studies conflicts from the point of view of social regulation of the needs, interests, actions of subjects, as well as conflicting actions corresponding to their nature. Cultural studies studies conflicts between different entities, individuals, social communities, and social institutions. The subject of cultural analysis of conflicts is ideas (religious and secular), traditions and customs, beliefs and beliefs. Conflict cultural studies reveals the influence of spiritual culture and civilization on interpersonal and social conflicts. Many other fields of science, such as history, art studies, economics, law, mathematics, pedagogy, political science, military science, etc., provide factual material for conflictology and serve as the field of application of its concepts. In a word, as a result of interdisciplinary research, conflictology gains the opportunity to determine specific, but also general laws of the emergence, development and termination of conflicts.

Literature

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